

OSMI – Principles of Open Science Monitoring

Self-Assessment of the National Open Access Monitor

Section 1: Relevance & Significance

All open science monitoring initiatives should be well-defined, relevant, and adaptable to diverse research contexts. They should support evidence-based policies and decisions, be developed through inclusive and participatory collaborative processes, and reflect the diversity of disciplines and stakeholders. Ensuring modularity, transparency, and consistency allows for reliable assessment while accommodating different needs and practices. Hence, to the extent possible, open science monitoring indicators should be:

1.1 Applicable and clear in scope:

Indicators should be applicable and relevant to the specific monitoring tasks. Their scope and meaning should be explicitly defined, and any limitations or constraints on their applicability should be clearly communicated.

Current status:

The Monitor's indicators are applicable to specific monitoring tasks through its 5-dashboard structure: National (country-level Open Science trends, historical snapshots and global benchmarking), RPO (institutional performance and peer comparison), RFO (funder compliance, grant-output linkages, peer comparison), Institutional Repository (repository content and OA contribution), and Researcher (individual research output and OA status).

Indicator scope and meaning are explicitly defined at:

- oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/methodology/methodological-approach
- oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/methodology/terminology

Limitations:

The Monitor reflects the quality of publicly available metadata, where source records are incomplete, this affects indicator accuracy. Phase I of the Monitor confirmed this: when records align, trust grows. HSS disciplines may be underrepresented due to lower PID adoption, and embargo tracking is constrained by variable repository metadata practices.

What we need to do:

Document limitations more prominently within the dashboard interface. Respond to Phase I feedback requesting "clearer guidance on interpreting dashboards" by developing interpretation guides and additional training for faculty and library staff.

1.2 Meaningful for planning and policy:

Indicators should align with broader public and global priorities and be accessible and useful for a wide range of stakeholders. They should enable the relevant stakeholders to design and evaluate context-specific monitoring systems, fostering evidence-informed policies, decisions and actions over time.

Current status:

Indicators align with national and European priorities. Nationally, they support Ireland's National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2030 goal to reach 100% OA of publicly funded publications by 2030, and align with the HEA Performance Framework (strategic, flexible, responsive, evidence-based). Globally, indicators feed into the EOSC Observatory, enabling European benchmarking.

The Monitor is publicly accessible and enables evidence-informed decisions and actions through context-specific dashboards (National, RFO, RPO, Repository, Researcher). Stakeholders can act on what they observe: researchers claim outputs and sync with ORCID, Dashboard Managers (70+ organisations currently) upload DOIs to correct institutional affiliations, and organisations disambiguate records. Phase I demonstrated this in practice: metadata improvements at Research Ireland and Maynooth University resulted from Monitor-informed action.

What we need to do:

Collect case studies documenting how Monitor data has informed policy and planning decisions. Phase II will expand indicators to support broader Open Research policy.

1.3 Co-created:

Indicators should be co-created with the research communities involved and, where appropriate, with the relevant non-academic communities, through public consultation and dialogue, ensuring the inclusion of underrepresented groups. The development and adoption of indicators should be driven by active participation from relevant stakeholders, grounded in community-driven activities and priorities.

Current status:

The Monitor was co-created through public consultation and community-driven development. A national stakeholder survey (February 2023) defined tender requirements and the OA definition, ensuring indicators reflect community priorities. The NORF National OA Monitoring Project Advisory Group, with representatives from RPOs, RFOs, and the research community, guided development. Design was further informed by consultation with Danish and French national monitoring providers.

Ongoing co-creation continues: 70+ organisations have registered Dashboard Managers who curate data, validate records, and provide feedback. Direct collaboration with organisations (e.g., Research Ireland, Maynooth University) has driven metadata improvements. Training webinars and the helpdesk maintain continuous dialogue.

Limitations:

Engagement has focused primarily on academic stakeholders (RPOs, RFOs, libraries). Non-academic communities and underrepresented groups have not been systematically included.

What we need to do:

Launch Phase II stakeholder survey to co-create requirements for expanded Open Research monitoring. Broaden consultation to include non-academic stakeholders and underrepresented research communities.

1.4 Inclusive:

Indicators should reflect the diversity of stakeholders, academic disciplines, languages, and the economic, sociocultural contexts and geopolitical constraints of the research landscape being monitored. They should account for gender equality, region-specific, and infrastructural needs. Additionally, they should embrace the richness of diverse knowledge systems, epistemologies, and knowledge producers, and explicitly address potential biases and historical inequities in knowledge production.

Current status:

The Monitor covers all Irish-affiliated research outputs regardless of the producer's sector, academic, industry, health, government, or independent researchers. Every person and organisation with research outputs is represented. Indicators are disaggregated by Fields of Science to capture disciplinary diversity. The platform is publicly accessible without institutional login or subscription barriers, and context-specific dashboards serve varied stakeholder needs.

Limitations:

Indicators are not currently disaggregated by gender or region within Ireland. HSS disciplines are underrepresented due to lower PID adoption, a known limitation of bibliometric data sources. The platform operates in English only.

What we need to do:

Consider gender and regional disaggregation where metadata supports it. Address HSS underrepresentation through targeted metadata improvement. Evaluate multilingual accessibility for Phase II.

1.5 Modular:

Indicator frameworks should be modular, enabling different communities to assemble indicator sets that best suit their specific needs. To support diversity and inclusion while ensuring both global comparability and local adaptability, these frameworks should incorporate a mix of quantitative and qualitative approaches, including case studies.

Current status:

The Monitor provides modularity through its 5-dashboard structure (National, RPO, RFO, Repository, Researcher) and filtering and breakdown capabilities allowing users to customise views by time period, Fields of Science and other dimensions. The quantitative framework (oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/methodology/methodological-approach) is principle-based, with initial indicators derived from the national stakeholder survey. Users can request additional indicators, which are evaluated for implementation.

By design, all users of each dashboard type see the same indicators, this supports transparency and comparability. Global comparability is further enabled through EOSC Observatory integration.

Limitations:

The Monitor currently provides quantitative indicators only. Qualitative approaches (case studies, narrative evidence) are not yet incorporated.

What we need to do:

Phase II will introduce qualitative evidence through systematic collection of case studies from organisations, funders, and repositories documenting how they use the Monitor for decision-making.

1.6 Reliable:

The level of scientific consensus around the reliability of each indicator needs to be made explicit. To ensure transparency, any indicator that is experimental or still under development should be clearly identified and labelled as such.

Current status:

Indicators use community-accepted definitions with explicit methodology documentation. OA routes follow the Budapest Open Access Initiative definition. Journal business models (Gold, Diamond, Hybrid, Transformative) use established sources: DOAJ, the ISSN-GOLD-OA methodology, Diamond Discovery Hub, and Plan S Transformative Journals data. APC data comes from OpenAPC. All definitions and construction methods are documented at oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/methodology/terminology.

The Monitor relies on the OpenAIRE Graph, one of the world's largest scholarly knowledge graphs with 336M+ research products from trusted data sources (<https://graph.openaire.eu/>). The Graph is open, transparent, and continuously validated through technical and community processes.

What we need to do:

Ensure any new indicators introduced in Phase II are clearly labelled if experimental or under development.

1.7 Consistent:

Indicators should be consistent to facilitate comparability between institutions, countries, regions, research areas and disciplines over time.

Current status:

Indicators are consistent across all institutions, funders, and time periods. The Monitor draws from a single source, the OpenAIRE Graph, applying uniform methodologies: same deduplication algorithms, same OA classification definitions, same Fields of Science taxonomy, same affiliation matching. This ensures comparability between Irish RPOs, RFOs, repositories, and researchers.

The 5-dashboard structure presents the same underlying indicators tailored to each stakeholder view, maintaining methodological consistency while serving different user needs. Time-series analysis uses consistent definitions across all periods, enabling longitudinal comparison. European-level comparability is enabled through EOSC Observatory integration using harmonised standards.

What we need to do:

Maintain methodological consistency as Phase II introduces new indicators. Document any changes to definitions or methodology to preserve comparability over time.

Section 2: Transparency & Reproducibility

Open science monitoring should, wherever possible, prioritize the use of open, transparent, and reproducible information, including metadata. It should further draw on infrastructures and methodologies that adhere to shared, agreed-upon principles and rely on publicly accessible data sources. In this context, to the extent possible, open science monitoring systems should prioritize:

2.1 Openness:

Monitoring initiatives should rely on open scholarly infrastructures with open input and output data as defined in the 2021 UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science. All software used throughout the monitoring process should be open source, versioned, and published openly with clear, comprehensive documentation on platforms that facilitate collaboration, contribution, and reuse. Output data, when not protected for copyright, privacy, contractual terms, or other legal or ethical reasons, should be open by default and distributed under an open licence.

Current status:

The Monitor is built entirely on open scholarly infrastructure. It relies on the OpenAIRE Graph, freely available under CC-BY licences, with versioned dumps deposited to Zenodo every six months (doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3516917) and main part of the EOSC EU Node infrastructure. OpenAIRE infrastructure is open source with documentation at graph.openaire.eu/docs/.

Output data is open by default:

- Full dataset accessible via OAI-PMH (oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/oai) and in Zenodo
- Data downloadable from dashboards
- All under open licence

The Monitor aligns with the 2021 UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science.

What we need to do:

Ensure that this level of openness is maintained

2.2 Quality of sources:

Input data for each indicator should be of high accuracy, comprehensive coverage, and up-to-date timeliness. As appropriate these aspects should be evaluated and publicly documented for each indicator, ensuring transparency and reliability. In addition, all indicators and their underlying data should be updated regularly and in a timely manner to enable effective monitoring of changes over time.

Current status:

- **Accuracy:** The Monitor relies on the OpenAIRE Graph, which applies documented quality assurance processes: metadata validation, deduplication algorithms, and organisation disambiguation via OpenOrgs (graph.openaire.eu/docs/graph-production-workflow/). Repositories are validated through OpenAIRE PROVIDE (<https://provide.openaire.eu/>) before integration.
- **Transparency:** Users can verify data quality directly. Every dashboard allows drill-down to browse underlying research outputs and view their full metadata. The Upload DOIs feature lets users check publications against Monitor metadata, immediately revealing any gaps or discrepancies. Dashboard Managers can validate institutional data, upload DOIs to correct affiliations, and flag issues via the helpdesk.
- **Timeliness:** The OpenAIRE Graph updates monthly.
- **Continuous improvement:** Direct collaboration with users drives quality improvements. Phase I showed this in practice, noticeable metadata improvements since launch, especially where we worked directly with users (e.g., Research Ireland, Maynooth University). Text mining for funder acknowledgements strengthened publication-funder linkages, significantly improving RFO dashboard completeness. The Graph also uses mining algorithms for other enrichments (affiliations, citations, subject classification).

What we need to do:

Continue collaboration with users to resolve data quality issues. Document known limitations more visibly within the platform.

2.3 Public documentation of sources and methodology:

All indicators should be accompanied by publicly available documentation detailing data collection methods, provenance, processing steps, and implementation choices. This documentation should rigorously specify the origin, version, and licensing of each data point to ensure clear and reliable provenance. Additionally, any indicators generated using artificial intelligence must be explicitly identified.

Current status:

All indicators are accompanied by public documentation. The Monitor methodology pages (oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/methodology/) document indicator definitions, terminology, and how constructed attributes are built. Detailed data collection methods, provenance, processing steps, and aggregation workflows are documented in the OpenAIRE Graph documentation (graph.openaire.eu/docs/).

Database versions are deposited to Zenodo with documentation, licensing (CC-BY), and version history. Sources for specific indicators are referenced in the terminology pages (e.g., DOAJ, OpenAPC, Plan S, Diamond Discovery Hub, Budapest OA Initiative).

AI and inference-based indicators: Indicators using AI or inference methods are explicitly identified and documented. This includes Fields of Science classification, Sustainable Development Goals classification, and text mining for funder acknowledgements. Each methodology is described in the terminology and Graph documentation.

What we need to do:

Ensure Phase II indicators maintain the same documentation standard, with explicit identification of any AI-based methodologies.

2.4 Reproducibility and reusability:

To ensure reproducibility, each indicator should be fully traceable, with versioning and a clear record of any modifications over time, ensuring data integrity and understandability. Furthermore, all monitoring results and indicator outcomes should be as reusable as possible.

Current status:

- **Traceability:** Every indicator is fully traceable. Users can drill down from any statistic to browse individual research outputs and their full metadata, ensuring transparency of what feeds each indicator.
- **Versioning:** The OpenAIRE Graph is deposited to Zenodo every six months with full documentation and a public changelog documents modifications over time (graph.openaire.eu/changelog).
- **Reusability:** Everything is open. Indicator construction happens within the OpenAIRE Graph, where all code and methodologies are open source and documented. Where no code exists, it is because calculations are simple counts. The full dataset is accessible via OAI-PMH (oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/oai) and downloadable from dashboards under open licence (CC-BY).

What we need to do:

Consider maintaining an Irish Monitor-specific changelog if indicator definitions evolve in Phase II.

2.5 Comprehensive metadata:

Monitoring outputs should be annotated with detailed and, where possible, standardized metadata to ensure data findability and usability for humans and machines. When relevant and appropriate persistent identifiers should be used to identify research outputs and resources as part of the monitoring process, to improve openness, provenance, citability, and transparency.

Current status:

- **Standardised metadata:** All metadata is standardised to OpenAIRE Guidelines (guidelines.openaire.eu), which adapt international standards from RDA, COUNTER, COAR, and DataCite. This ensures findability and usability for both humans and machines.
- **Persistent identifiers:** PIDs are used extensively throughout:
 - Research outputs: DOI, Handle, PubMed ID, PubMed Central ID, arXiv ID
 - Researchers: ORCID
 - Organisations: ROR, GRID, ISNI
 - Funders: Open Funder Registry
 - Projects: Grant IDs
- **Findability:** Data is findable for humans via dashboards with full drill-down to record-level metadata. For machines, the full dataset is harvestable via OAI-PMH (oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/oai).

What we need to do:

Continue encouraging PID adoption across the Irish research ecosystem, particularly in disciplines with lower coverage.

2.6 Consideration of community-defined and recognized principles:

To the extent possible, monitoring outputs should be compliant with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility and Ethics), TRUST (Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology) and other relevant principles. Furthermore, a greater focus on data justice could help counteract global power imbalances and ensure equitable data access for all, including marginalized communities.

Current status:

- **FAIR:** Fully compliant.
 - Findable: PIDs used throughout (DOI, ORCID, ROR), standardised metadata, indexed in OpenAIRE Graph

- Accessible: Open licence (CC-BY/CC-0), publicly accessible without login, OAI-PMH harvestable
- Interoperable: OpenAIRE Guidelines following RDA, COUNTER, COAR, DataCite standards; EOSC Interoperability Framework compliant
- Reusable: Clear licensing, full documentation, open code
- **CARE:** Dashboard Managers give Irish organisations authority to control and validate their own data. The Monitor is managed by IReL (project manager) with OpenAIRE, with oversight from the HEA Advisory Group, ensuring Irish research community governance. No commercial interests influence the monitoring process.
- **TRUST:**
 - Transparency: Full methodology documentation, open data
 - Responsibility: GDPR compliant, privacy policy published
 - User focus: 5 context-specific dashboards, helpdesk, training programme
 - Sustainability: Built on established OpenAIRE infrastructure, long-term EOSC integration
 - Technology: Open source, documented, versioned
- **Data justice:** The Monitor is publicly accessible without institutional barriers, ensuring equitable access. All outputs are under open licence enabling reuse.

What we need to do:

Explicitly document CARE and TRUST compliance on the platform.

2.7 Contextualized communication:

The communication of open science monitoring outcomes should be carefully tailored to prevent oversimplification and misinterpretation, ensuring clarity and relevance for all stakeholders. This includes providing clear, accessible explanations of indicators and conclusions to promote understanding and engagement from the general public.

Current status:

Communication of monitoring outcomes is tailored to different stakeholders. Methodology documentation (oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/methodology/) provides clear explanations of indicator definitions, construction, and limitations. The terminology page explains each attribute with definitions and "how we build it" descriptions, preventing misinterpretation.

An extensive engagement and training programme ensures stakeholders understand the Monitor (oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/engagement-training):

- Stakeholder webinars introducing the platform
- Targeted training sessions for RPOs, RFOs, and repository managers
- "Open Insights Sessions" covering specific topics: data quality, text mining, repository integration, usability, future pathways

- OpenAPC and OpenOrgs training
- Conference and workshop participation (OSFair, CONUL, IRC)
- All presentations and materials publicly available via Zenodo and YouTube

The helpdesk provides one-to-one support for questions and clarifications.

What we need to do:

Develop clearer dashboard interpretation guides for non-specialist users per Phase I feedback. Continue engagement programme in Phase II.

2.8 Disclosure of conflicts of interest:

Open science actors should disclose any conflict of interest when monitoring is undertaken.

Current status:

No conflicts of interest identified.

What we need to do:

Disclose any conflicts of interest, if any identified.